

Unifying Bottom-Up and Top-Down Attention Models for Social Robots

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Abstract—Overt visual attention plays a key role in social human-human interactions. In previous work, it has been shown that humans similarly expect a robot to have an expressive gazing behaviour. In humans, both bottom-up perceptual stimuli and top-down inner motivations contribute to the visual attention and gazing behaviour. Designing an overt attention model for social robots requires taking both these aspects into account. In this extended abstract, we expose why currently available attention models do not suit social robotic applications. Then, we present our current and future work on visual attention modelling for social robots. Finally, we sketch out the next steps we will take in our research.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is becoming more and more frequent for social robots to be deployed in real world scenarios. Every day they face partially unstructured social situations: for instance, while a robot receptionist might usually welcome people and provide them information in the same area of a building, the structure of the groups of people meeting with the robot can differ every time. These situations require the robot to have a fluid and natural interaction with the humans, who expect its behaviour to fit the social dynamics. One of the most prominent aspects in social robots behaviour is the visual attention, due to the importance that this has for humans in communication and intimacy-establishment. Research has investigated the role of gazing in HRI, showing that humans perceive robots' overt visual attention as a pseudo-social signal. While it is still unclear whether the joint attention induced by robot gaze has the same effectiveness as the human one, as it seems that reaction time might differ [1]–[3], studies indicate that robots' gaze is something people notice and care about [4], [5].

In this paper, we will focus on the technological aspect of robot gazing behaviour and overt visual attention, rather than on design or human-focused aspects [6]. A social robot gazing behaviour has a relevant impact on human interaction and it should follow human norms: this means avoiding overly long fixations at the same person and too quick glances to the people that are part of the interacting group; it also means averting gaze from time to time, just as humans do (and fellow humans expect them to do).

A. Previous work

Previous work on the technological aspect of social robots attention can be divided in three categories: biologically inspired, heuristics-based and data-driven [6]. Either *bottom-up* or *top-down* processes regulate their results.

Biologically inspired attention models derive from research on humans and primates reactions to perceptual stimuli [7]. They are based on bottom-up processes. Despite being able to accurately model biological reactions to RGB inputs, they are not suited for social attention modelling since they do not consider any semantic aspect.

Heuristics-based approaches define rules to regulate robot overt visual attention in specific situations that require explicit and transparent modelling: for instance, intimacy and turn-taking tasks [8]. These models are based on top-down processes. In this case, despite the highly social motivation of most of these methodologies, the heuristics defined usually fit a very narrow portion of the social contexts spectrum. They cannot adapt when applied to other dynamics rather than those they were originally meant for.

Data-driven approaches usually exploit RGB or RGB-D information, applying machine learning techniques to model attention behaviours starting from the provided dataset. In this case, machine learning techniques could allow generalisation over some of the dynamic aspects of a social interaction: for instance the number of participants in a discussion or their group formation. However, these methods are usually based on human-related semantic aspects, such as people location in the scene, their gaze patterns, their orientation [9], etc.

Fig. 1. In the left image, a purely perceptual attention model generates fixation on H2 while H1 is speaking, causing confusion in H1. In the right image, a purely semantic attention model generates fixation on H1 while a loud sound occurs in the room. The robot would have been expected to turn toward the loud sound as well.

Biological [10] and psychological [11] research showed that visual attention focus in primates and humans is the result of a combination of bottom-up and top-down processes. Perceptual stimuli and semantic knowledge concur in generating the following gaze target. Currently, our research is focusing on understanding how to build a context-dependent data-driven overt attention model for social robots, overcoming the limitations of the existing models (Fig. 1). In particular, these are the key aspects we investigate:

- 1) The design of a social attention model exploiting the concurrency between perceptual and semantic stimuli.
- 2) The perceived quality of the human-robot interaction when using this model to generate gazing behaviours.

II. A COMPREHENSIVE DATA-DRIVEN MODEL

We consider data-driven models to suit the task since their generalisation capabilities would allow –when trained on appropriate datasets– to generate attention focuses that are the result of the concurrency between perceptual stimuli, semantic stimuli and regulating behaviours, such as gaze aversion and joint attention. Moreover, fine tuning the model with different datasets could allow modelling attention for specific situations.

Despite advancements in related fields, such as Video Salient Object Detection (VSOD), social robots attention is still mostly engineered to follow simple heuristic-based rules. Moreover, most of the models proposed in literature do not provide a way to extend their range of action to different tasks and contexts. In our current work, we are focusing on the potentiality of deep learning algorithms for sequential data in social attention modelling. In this case, we are considering not only purely RGB data, but also semantic and spatial information about the objects in the scene. The set of information included to establish the robot’s focus of attention comes from the previously cited concept of concurrency between top-down and bottom-up stimuli to establish the focus of attention.

A. Dataset recording

To prove the potential of a context-oriented approach, we recorded a dataset of interactions between colleagues during common office activities: for instance, coffee breaks and professional meetings. The recordings took place in October and November 2022 in PAL Robotics in Barcelona, Spain. Overall, we collected 11 video clips, each one between 31 and 46 seconds long. We mounted the camera on the upper part of the chest of the experimenter in order to avoid the influence of head movements (that would have occurred with eg a head-mounted camera), while providing a first person point-of-view. At this point, we are not yet considering two important social attention aspects: head movements and audio cues (the videos shown to the participants were muted). These aspects will be investigated in future work.

B. Ground truth collection

The acquisition of a human baseline for the focus of attention was crowd-sourced on the Prolific platform. Various proposed VSOD solutions proved gaze direction recordings

to be an effective ground truth [16], [17]. In this case, we recorded gaze directions of online gathered participants. We obtained data from 60 people ranging from 20 to 58 years ($M = 25$, $mean = 28.58$, $SD = 8.70$, 30 female). Each participant watched 4 randomly extracted videos from the dataset. We designed a website to run the experiment using JsPsych [18], which allows to define experiment pipelines in javascript and to enable gaze estimation via WebGazer [19]. For each video frame, we collected multiple visual attention focus (one from each participant watching the video). Using this information and taking into account WebGazer accuracy limitations, we generated the probability distribution for the human visual attention focus over the video frame (Fig. 2, bottom right). This probability distribution will be used as the ground truth during the model training process. Finally, the model should be able to generate probability distributions for visual attention over video frames.

Fig. 2. A deep-learning architecture that will be tested to generate probability distributions over video frames. Here, the semantic information obtained as the encoding generated by a semantic segmentation model is concatenated with the output of a ConvLSTM model, in charge of extracting perceptually-salient visual patterns over time. Finally, a multilayer perceptron generates a quantization for the probability distribution of the next gazing goal over the input frame.

III. NEXT STEPS

Tests are currently ongoing to identify an architecture that is capable to capture semantic and perceptual aspects, with a candidate in Fig. 2. At this stage, the results obtained will be compared with other gazing behaviour generation systems and VSOD models, evaluating their performance on the previously described dataset. We will then implement the model on PAL Robotics’ ARI, to understand how people perceive the generated robot’s gazing behaviour in a social context. For this step, we will define an experiment to compare the proposed model with previous ones in terms of social perception to establish the effectiveness of the proposed method. During experiment design process, we will take inspiration from previous works in the field.

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